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Abstract: Along with the creation of an innovative environment in the educational system, the issues of innovative production of educational processes, development of innovative education, trends and prospects, implementation of innovative activities in the development of innovative education are discussed.

Key words: innovation, innovative environment, innovative activity, innovative education, innovative trends, science, educational system.

Any educational institution that strives to maintain its viability under market conditions will eventually create something new in the field of science or in the personnel training system, implement new ideas, that is, the materialization of ideas and potential in the markets. It should be sold to buyers.

Also, in today's modern conditions, building the future of our country through the use of innovative technological achievements in world pedagogy is becoming an important factor of development. During the period of rapid development of our country observed in recent years, there is a great need for specialists who think critically, master information and communication technologies, create and implement innovations. This situation requires the development of programs that help to increase quality indicators in education by introducing innovations, modern interactive and creative teaching methods, and supporting pedagogical research.

The establishment of the activity of educational institutions on the basis of commercialism may certainly distract them from their functional tasks, but engaging in scientific and innovative activities will ultimately provide educational institutions with material self-sufficiency. It creates an opportunity. Along with the creation of an innovative environment that is effective in our republic, the activation of the innovative activity of educational institutions has become an objective need. The processes of creation and implementation of innovations also consist of certain cycles. From this point of view, the innovation cycle is a set of activities that continue consistently in time dimensions and differ from each other by acquiring functionally separate content at different stages that are the same in terms of importance.

The processes of creation and implementation of innovations in the introduction of innovative activities of the educational institution also consist of certain cycles. From this point of view, the innovation process is a set of activities that continue consistently in time dimensions and differ from each other by acquiring functionally separate content at different stages that are the same in terms of importance. Fundamental ideas and knowledge that serve as a basis for innovation, and their practical application will lead to the following results:

- identifying unpromising projects and making the right decision;
- further improvement in the process of implementation of the innovative idea;

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- there will be an opportunity to adapt the innovation to its technological features, to the nature of the systems responsible for management and organizational activity. The functions of using financial resources of innovative potential are:

- ensuring the arrival of financial resources required for the introduction of innovations;
- creation of conditions for appropriate provision of financial resources for innovative processes; - improvement of implementation of innovative processes;

- creation of conditions for the creation of innovations, and encouragement; - to support the creation of innovative projects that meet various needs related to the functional activity and development of the existing innovative system;

- to ensure the optimal cost effectiveness of innovative projects. Y. Schumpeter defines the following functional tasks of entities operating in the innovation field:

- to carry out a commercial analysis in order to identify potential consumers who will be interested in adopting innovations;

- to find authors of promising ideas, sources that provide an opportunity for functional activity;

- organization of the processes of creation of innovations and their implementation;

- to support the introduction of innovations into practice. - improvement of innovative work in the field of innovative activity at the stage of materialization of new ideas discovered in the field of science; The teacher should purposefully organize personal relations in the group at the stage before the formation of the team. For this, he/she must have a highly developed communicative learning-attitude and aptitude and ability to establish relationships, understanding of learners.

Coordination of innovation groups activity and the mechanisms of regulation of activity in it through management functions depends on the implementation of the following:

- correct definition of socio-economic and scientific-technical perspectives; - accumulation of funds necessary for the implementation of various scientific researches and innovations;

- coordination of innovative activities; - innovation promotion; to strengthen competitiveness in the innovative field and attach importance to the supply of potential personnel in the implementation of innovative activities in the educational system;

- formation of scientific and innovative infrastructure;

- to ensure that the planned innovations are socially and economically oriented;

- raising the social status of innovative activities in the educational system; - regulation of innovative processes in the educational system on a regional scale;

Educational institutions that have organized innovative groups have competitiveness. This, in turn, serves in the organization and integration of various programs. Institutions that have formed innovative groups are leaders, that is, they indicate the active participation of educational institutions and strong external relations with foreign partners.

These institutions are comfortable, that is, they provide security and are distinguished by a complete infrastructure (medicine, sports, media library, psychologist-pedagogical observation, information center, etc.). In this case, the institutions also effectively carry out innovative activities, that is, they develop new organizational technologies, new programs and methods.

We can group these as follows:

1. Innovations related to the purpose and content of education;

2. Innovations aimed at changing the methods, tools, techniques, technologies used in the pedagogical process;

3. Innovations aimed at changing the forms and methods of education and training;
4. Innovations aimed at changing the organization and management of the educational institution's leadership, pedagogues and students.

Conclusion: In the development of innovative education, the above-mentioned innovative activity implementation groups should choose the most optimal options, solve the necessary issues for efficient management of innovations. In the development of innovative education, it is desirable to make optimal decisions about innovations in the educational system, to successfully solve the issues of creating an electronic information system and its effective use.

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